

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA):IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Enhanced Oral Bioavailability Through Nanoparticle- Based Solid Lipid Carrier: A Novel Approach To Drug Deliver

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 16 Sep 2024

Accepted: 20 Sep 2024

Published: 30 Sep 2024

Keywords:

Hot homogenization technique, microemulsion technique, solid lipids carriers, nanoparticles, oral delivery, lymphatic absorption.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13863137

ABSTRACT

Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) offer promising properties for drug delivery due to their use of physiologically acceptable lipids. These nanoparticles are particularly notable for their versatility in encapsulating a wide range of substances, including labile compounds like proteins and peptides, as well as lipophilic and hydrophilic drugs. SLNs are beneficial in drug delivery systems as they provide protection against degradation, both in vitro and in vivo. This protective capability is crucial for maintaining drug stability and efficacy. Additionally, SLNs can regulate drug release and target specific areas, enhancing the therapeutic impact of the medication. One of the key advantages of SLNs is their nanometer-scale size, which contributes to their ability to improve the oral bioavailability of poorly soluble drugs. By improving solubility and stability, SLNs can significantly enhance the therapeutic efficacy of such medications. The review explores the various aspects of SLNs, including their in vivo behavior, which involves understanding how they interact within the body and their ultimate fate. It also delves into the Physico-chemical characteristics of SLNs, such as size, surface properties, and drug loading capacity, which are critical for their performance. Additionally, the review discusses the lymphatic mechanism through which SLNs are transported and absorbed, highlighting their potential for targeted delivery. Finally this review covers the fabrication techniques used to produce SLNs, providing insight into the methods that optimize their performance for therapeutic applications.

INTRODUCTION

Oral drug delivery systems (DDS) face a number of difficulties due to the gastrointestinal (GI) tract's function as a physiological and chemical barrier. Bioavailability is aided by the

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

development of composite formulation techniques, and this new subject has a bright future ahead of it. In this regard, the formulation of medications that are poorly soluble in water and the creation of solubilized phases are becoming increasingly intriguing due to the growing body of information regarding lipids. (Setzer Constantine and others, 2010)¹. For a Solid lipid Nanoparticles for Oral delivery of Poorly Soluble Drugs very long time, lipophilic medications have been transported by lipid matrices, which increase the pharmaceuticals' oral bioavailability. Different carriers of lipid particles have been developed. Due to their unique amphiphilic nature, phospholipids can dissolve in water and take on a variety of shapes based on their particular characteristics. Typically, they arrange themselves into lipid bilayers or form micelles, with the hydrophilic head groups facing the water on both sides and the hydrophobic tails oriented toward each other. Phospholipids are well-suited to be employed as excipients for medications that are not very soluble in water due to these special qualities. Therefore, it is important to remember that the increased solubility of lipophilic medications from lipid-based systems will likely result from intra-luminal processing, which is what the drug undergoes prior to absorption, rather than from the lipid itself. A variety of oils, surfactants, and co-solvents can be found in lipid-based drug delivery systems. These are among the most widely used strategies for overcoming obstacles to absorption and increasing the bioavailability of poorly soluble medications. In addition, factors such as the mean emulsion size and lipid digestion are among the variables influencing the drug's bioavailability from lipid-based formulations, droplet diameter, drug lipophilicity, and lipid type. Lipid formulations can lessen the inherent restriction of slowly and

incompletely dissolving medications that are not very soluble in water and help generate solubilized phases from which absorption may take place. After lipid absorption, intral aminal processing is most likely the source of the solubilized phases. When drugs are administered in combination with lipids, it can affect how well they are absorbed. While most substances taken orally enter the bloodstream through the portal vein, some highly lipophilic drugs enter the bloodstream directly through the intestinal lymphatics, increasing their oral bioavailability²⁻⁸.

SOLID LIPID NANOPARTICLE:

To create an emulsion, a melted lipid phase is stirred rapidly in a heated surfactant solution. This was the first method of employing lipid micro particles, as reported by (Eldem et al). The lipid recrystallizes and solid micro particles are created when this emulsion cools to room temperature. Oral administration of the resulting products, dubbed 'lipid Nano pellets,' has been explored. Utilizing a sonication technique, Domb described lipospheres. Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLN) are a potential solution to circumvent the limitations of conventional colloidal systems, including emulsions, liposomes, and polymeric nanoparticles. SLNs have been created with comparable objectives in mind. To distribute drugs under control and target them specifically, SLNs are biocompatible and biodegradable. With a mean particle size between 50 and 1000 nm, these colloidal carriers are made of a lipid matrix that is dispersed in water or an aqueous surfactant solution. The matrix should be solid at both room temperature and body temperature. Composed of a monolayer of phospholipids covering, they have a solid hydrophobic core. The medication is within the solid core Scattered or dissolved inside the lipid layer, they might transport hydrophilic or lipophilic drugs.⁹⁻¹².

Fig 1: Diagram of solid lipid nanoparticle

ADVANTAGES OF SLN OVER POLYMERIC NANOPARTICLE:

Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) offer several notable advantages over polymeric nanoparticles and other colloidal carriers such as fat emulsions and liposomes. One significant benefit is their reduced uptake by cells in the Reticuloendothelial System (RES), particularly for particles sized between 120–200 nm, which helps to avoid extensive liver and spleen filtration. The lipid matrix of SLNs, composed of physiological lipids, further reduces the risk of both acute and long-term toxicity. Additionally, SLNs are simpler to fabricate compared to bio polymeric nanoparticles, facilitating their production. SLNs enable targeted and controlled drug release, enhancing the precision of therapeutic delivery. They also provide increased stability for medications, with some formulations maintaining stability for up to three years. This stability is crucial for ensuring the efficacy of the encapsulated drug over time. Furthermore, SLNs can improve the bioavailability of both hydrophilic and hydrophobic drugs, making them versatile carriers for a range of therapeutic agents. The use of biodegradable lipids in SLNs enhances their safety profile, and the avoidance of organic solvents in

their manufacturing process adds to their environmental and biological compatibility. SLNs are also suitable for large-scale production and sterilization, which is essential for widespread clinical use. Additionally, they offer chemical protection for volatile substances incorporated within the lipid matrix. These combined advantages make SLNs a promising choice for advanced drug delivery systems, leveraging the benefits of various colloidal systems while mitigating their drawbacks.

DISADVANTAGES;

Solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) face several challenges that impact their efficacy in drug delivery. One significant issue is their relatively low capacity for drug loading, which can limit the amount of therapeutic agent that can be incorporated. Additionally, there is a risk of drug expulsion during polymeric transformation processes that may occur over time, particularly during storage. SLNs also have high water content in their dispersions, ranging from 70% to 99.9%, which can affect their stability and performance. Furthermore, the production process can lead to partitioning effects that limit the loading capacity for water-soluble drugs. Addressing these

challenges is crucial for optimizing the use of SLNs in drug delivery systems¹³⁻²⁰.

LIPID MATERIAL FOR ORAL ADMINISTRATION:

The term "lipid" refers to a wide range of substances, such as fatty acids, steroids, waxes, triglycerides, and partial glycerides. Nonetheless, the matrix must remain in a solid state at room temperature. To achieve this, lipids are selected based on an assessment of their physicochemical structure, polymorphism, crystallinity, and miscibility. Comparing mono- and di-glycerides to very pure lipids like monoacid triglycerides may also improve drug solubility in the lipid matrix composition. Mixtures of mono-, di-, and

triglycerides with fatty acids of different chain lengths and degrees of unsaturation make up naturally occurring oils and fats. The melting points of these lipids rise with the length Polysorbate of Polysorbate the fatty acid chain and fall with the degree of unsaturation. Lipids that form highly crystalline particles with a flawless lattice—such as monoacid triglycerides—can lead to drug ejection during storage. Therefore, the chemical makeup of the lipid is crucial. To produce lipid nanoparticles that are physically and chemically stable, the appropriate surfactant must be used at the proper concentration (Severino Patricia, et al., 2012)²¹⁻²⁷.

Table 1: Different Lipids and Surfactants used for preparation of SLNs²

LIPIDS	SURFACTANTS
Triacylglycerols: Tricarpin Triaurin Trimyrustin Tripalmitin	Phospholipids: Soy lecithin Egg lecithin Phosphatidylcholine
Acylglycerols: Glycerol Monostearate Glycerol behenate Glycerol Palmitostearate	Ethylene oxide/propylene oxide copolymers: Poloxamer 188 Poloxamer 182 Poloxamer 407 Poloxamine 908
Fatty acids: Stearic acid Palmitic acid Decanoic acid Behenic acid	Sorbitan ethylene oxide/propylene oxide copolymers: Polysorbate 20 Polysorbate 60 Polysorbate 80
Waxes: Cetyl palmitate	Alkyaryl polyether alcohol polymers: Tyloxapol
Cyclic complexes: Cyclodextrin	Bile salts: Sodium cholate Sodium glycocholate Sodium taurocholate
Hard fat types: Witepsol W 35 Witepsol H 35	Alcohols: Ethanol Butanol

LYMPHATIC TRANSPORT MECHANISM OF SLNs:

It has been possible to effectively generate several of these molecules with acceptable oral

bioavailability through the use of lipid-based drug delivery vehicles. The efficiency with which lipophilic drug molecules can be delivered, particularly when combined with lipid-based

delivery systems, has rekindled interest in intestinal lymphatic drug transport. Most oral drugs quickly disperse throughout the cell after being absorbed into the enterocytes. They are then absorbed into the portal vein's capillaries and processed by the liver before entering the systemic circulation. On the other hand, highly lipophilic drug molecules have the ability to attach themselves to lymph lipoprotein in the enterocytes and enter the mesenteric (intestinal) lymphatic system, thereby avoiding the liver and entering the systemic circulation through the thoracic lymph duct. In addition to reduced first-pass metabolism for drugs transported lymphatically, the extremely

high drug concentrations in lymph (up to 1000 times higher than in plasma) often offer advantages for drug delivery, such as targeted delivery to lymph resident B and T lymphocytes and the ability to target the primary pathway of tumor metastasis (Porter CJH et al., 2001)29-35. Lipids are very desirable candidates for oral formulation carriers due to their unique qualities, which include their physiochemical diversity, biocompatibility, and demonstrated capacity to increase the oral bioavailability of lipophilic, poorly water soluble drugs through selective lymphatic uptake.

Fig 2 : A diagrammatic representation of the uptake of lipids by the intestinal lymphatic (Adapted from Florence TA, 2005)36

With the unique amphiphilic nature of phospholipids, absorption may occur. Depending on their unique qualities, they take on different forms in water. With the hydrophilic head group facing the water on both sides and the hydrophobic tails arranged against one another, they often form micelles or are arranged as lipid bilayers. Phospholipids have special qualities that make them ideal for use as excipients in drugs that are not very soluble in water. Therefore, it is important to remember that the increased solubility of lipophilic medications from lipid-based systems will probably result from intra-luminal processing, which is what the drug undergoes before absorption, rather than from the lipid itself (Setzer Constantine, 2010)1.

IN VIVO CASE OF LIPIDS IN HUMAN BODY:

The digestive system of an adult is capable of hydrolyzing between 100 and 140 g of fat per day. The intraluminal processing that lipids undergo before absorption is primarily responsible for the drug's solubility and bioavailability in the GI tract. Consequently, understanding how lipids move from the GI lumen to the circulatory system in the context of a robust digestive system is crucial for understanding the biopharmaceutical characteristics of oral lipid-based formulations and for the effective development of new products. Therefore, the focus of this section is to simplify the understanding of the entire process by dividing it into three distinct phases: (Sanjay Singh et al., 2009)37-40.

1. Digestive Phase
2. Absorption Phase
3. Circulatory Uptake

1) Digestive Phase:

The digestive phase initiates with the physical breakdown of lipid formulation into a coarse emulsion (lipid droplets $\sim 0.5 \mu\text{m}$) of high surface area due to shear produced by antral contraction, retropulsion, and gastric emptying. This is accompanied by the hydrolysis of fatty acid glyceryl esters by gastric lipase secreted from chief cells in the stomach (capable of functioning in an acidic environment), which act at the oil/water interface. The enzymatic hydrolysis reduces the TGs into its more polar products: monoglycerides (MGs) and fatty acids (FAs). Lipase cleaves the two ester bonds of the TG molecule, producing a molecule of di-glyceride and one free FA first, and then two molecules of free FAs and one molecule of MG (Fig. 2). The dispersed lipid digestion products, along with the undigested lipids, then empty into the duodenum. The undigested lipids and the dispersed lipid breakdown products then drain into the duodenum. Cholecystokinin is released into the portal circulation when FAs are present. This further prompts the pancreas to release TG lipase and co-lipase, which are necessary to aid in the digestion of TGs within emulsified particles. Therefore, when lipolytic compounds are generated, the autocatalytic process of lipolysis can improve

emulsification. Due to their water solubility, both enzymes work at the particle's water/lipid interface, hydrolyzing TGs to MGs and FAs. An illustration of the function of mixed bile salt micelles and lipase/co-lipase in the breakdown and solubilization of triglycerides is shown. Each triglyceride molecule is digested to generate two molecules of fatty acid and one molecule of monoglyceride, which is solubilized in the lumen of the gut.

2) Absorption Phase:

As a consequence of lipid digestion, colloidal species are created in the form of micelles, mixed micelles, vesicles, and free FAs. These are then absorbed by active transport, assisted diffusion, and passive diffusion across the enterocyte membrane. They are transported from the apical membrane to the smooth endoplasmic reticulum (ER) via a fatty acid-binding protein in the cytoplasm. In the smooth ER, FAs and MGs are resynthesized into TGs and phospholipids, respectively, which are transferred to the Golgi apparatus and stored in secretory vesicles to be released by exocytosis into the extracellular space via the basolateral membrane. The binding of the absorbed free drugs to chylomicrons, or intestinal lipoproteins, inside the enterocyte, is another crucial stage. These chylomicrons are colloidal and comparatively large ($<1 \mu\text{m}$ diameter), which ultimately results in the lipophilic compound's preferential intestinal lymphatic transit.

Fig 3: Schematic diagram of drug metabolism

The primary Phase I drug-metabolizing enzyme, cytochrome P450 3A4 (CYP 3A4), which is highly concentrated in enterocytes near the villus tip of the small intestine in humans, is typically exposed to the drug molecules during the absorption phase. Studies conducted across different laboratories have accounted for the role of these enzymes in increasing the bioavailability of drugs when co-administered with lipids, which is indicative of an additional pathway by which lipids enhance oral drug bioavailability.

3. Circulation Pathway:

The majority of drugs taken orally enter the systemic circulation by absorption into the portal blood. Nonetheless, several highly lipophilic medications ($\log P > 5$, solubility in TG > 50 mg/ml) avoid hepatic first-pass metabolism by

entering the systemic circulation through the lymphatic system. Consequently, drugs that are heavily metabolized and lipophilic could be suitable options for lipid-based drug delivery. When lipids (dietary or lipid-based formulations) are present, compounds with enhanced bioavailability are absorbed through the intestinal lymph because they are typically transported alongside the intestinal lipoproteins' long-chain TG lipid core, which is formed in the enterocyte following the re-esterification of free FAs and MGs. The portal blood is where short-chain TGs are mainly absorbed directly. Therefore, co-administration of lipids is necessary to increase lipoprotein production and facilitate drug transport via the lymphatic system.

Fig 4: Schematic diagram of increase in drug bioavailability

The following are some different ways that lipids can increase a drug's bioavailability: (a) The drug is dissolved in the intestinal fluid by the production of colloidal species, such as vesicles, mixed micelles, and micelles. (b) Interference with enterocyte-based metabolic processes and transport, which may alter drug uptake, efflux, disposition, and the synthesis of metabolites (M). (c) Through selective lymphatic uptake, this lessens first-pass drug metabolism because intestinal lymph flows directly to the systemic circulation.

PREPARATION OF SOLID LIPID NANOPARTICLE (SLNs):

Solid lipids, emulsifiers, and water/solvents comprise SLNs. Triglycerides (tri-stearin), partial glycerides (Imwitor), fatty acids (stearic acid,

palmitic acid), steroids (cholesterol), and waxes (cetyl palmitate) are examples of the lipids that can be employed. The lipid dispersion is stabilized by using a variety of emulsifiers and their combinations. Emulsifier combinations may work better together to prevent particle agglomeration. The basic production methods for SLNs are as follows:

- Hot homogenization technique
- Cold homogenization technique
- Microemulsion technique
- Solvent emulsification-diffusion technique
- Precipitation method
- W/O/W double emulsion method
- Spray drying method

Table 2: Schematic representation for the production of solid lipid nanoparticle by the hot and cold homogenization techniques.

Steps	Hot Homogenation Technique	Cold Homogenation Technique
Step 1	Melt lipid; dissolve or solubilize active ingredient in the lipid.	Melt lipid; dissolve or solubilize active ingredient in the lipid.

Step 2	Disperse melted lipid in hot aqueous surfactant solution.	Cooling and recrystallization of the active lipid mixture using liquid and nitrogen or dry ice.
Step 3	Preparation of pre-emulsion by means of a rotor-stator homogenizer.	Milling of the active lipid mixture by means of a ball mill or a jet mill.
Step 4	High-pressure homogenization above the melting point of the lipid.	Disperse lipid microparticles in cold aqueous surfactant solution.
Step 5	Cooling and recrystallization.	High-pressure homogenization at or below room temperature.

Solvent Emulsification/Evaporation:

Precipitation is used to create nanoparticle dispersions in o/w emulsions. The lipophilic substance is dissolved in an organic solvent that is water-miscible and emulsified in an aqueous phase, such as cyclohexane. Lipid precipitation in aqueous media creates a nanoparticle dispersion when the solvent evaporates. The amount of lipid present in the organic phase determines the mean particle size. Concerning the organic solvent, very tiny particles can be generated with modest fat loading (5% w/w). The absence of thermal stress is the method's benefit over the cold homogenization process. The use of organic solvents is counterproductive (Mehnert W et al., 2001)⁴¹. Additionally, due to the lipid's low solubility in the organic substance, these dispersions are typically rather diluted. Lipid concentrations in the final SLN dispersion typically range from 0.1 g/l; methods such as ultra-filtration.

Microemulsion Method:

Microemulsions are diluted to use this approach. The process involves agitating a mixture that is optically transparent between 65 and 70 degrees Celsius. This mixture is usually made of water, sodium monoethylphosphate, polysorbate 20, polysorbate 60, phosphatidylcholine, and low-melting fatty acids like stearic acid. The hot microemulsion is dispersed in cold water (2-3°C) under stirring; the volume ratio of hot microemulsion to cold water is in the range of 1:25 to 1:50. The dilution process is critically

determined by the composition of the microemulsion (Mukherjee S et al., 2009)⁴². Numerous studies have been conducted on the effects of experimental variables on the size and structure of the resulting SLN, including temperature, lyophilization, dispersing High concentrations of co-surfactants and surfactants (such as butanol) are required for formulation purposes but are less desirable for regulatory and application purposes (Wissing S et al., 2004)⁴³. The composition of the microemulsion plays a significant role in the dilution process. According to the literature, no additional energy is needed to achieve submicron particle sizes because the droplet structure is already present in the microemulsion. The velocity of the distribution processes is crucial in determining the particle size. Nanoparticle production was limited to solvents such as acetone, which rapidly diffuse into the aqueous phase; more lipophilic solvents yield larger particle sizes. The dilution stage results in significantly lower attainable levels compared to formulations based on high-pressure homogenization (HPH) (Mehnert W et al., 2001)⁴¹.

W/O/W Double Emulsion Method:

The scientific community has recently been introduced to a unique approach for preparing solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) loaded with hydrophilic drugs. This method is based on solvent emulsification-evaporation. Hydrophilic drugs are encapsulated in the internal water phase of a water-in-oil-in-water (w/o/w) double emulsion, along

with a stabilizer to prevent drug partitioning to the exterior water phase during solvent evaporation. Although sodium cromoglycate-containing SLNs were prepared by this process, the average particle size was in the micrometer range, making the term "lipospheres" less appropriate for these particles (Cortesi et al., 2002)⁴⁴.

SLNs Preparation Using Supercritical Fluids:

This method of producing SLNs is relatively new and benefits from solvent-less processing. The platform technology offers multiple versions for preparing both powders and nanoparticles. SLNs can be prepared using the rapid expansion of supercritical carbon dioxide solutions (RESS) technique. Carbon dioxide (99.99%) serves as an excellent solvent option for this process.

Spray Drying Method:

The spray drying method differs from lyophilization in that it converts an aqueous SLN dispersion into a pharmaceutical product. It is less expensive than lyophilization. However, particle aggregation can occur due to the high temperature, shear stresses, and partial melting of the particles. It is recommended to use lipids with a melting point $>70^{\circ}\text{C}$ for spray drying. Optimal results are achieved with an SLN concentration of 1% in a solution of trehalose in water or 20% trehalose in an ethanol-water mixture (10/90 v/v).

DRUGS INCORPORATION MODELS⁴⁵:

The physical and chemical properties of the lipid and active ingredient, solubility of the actives in the melted lipid, type and concentration of surfactants, manufacturing method, and production temperature all influence the types of

SLNs. This has led to the proposal of three incorporation models for investigation¹²:

Homogeneous Matrix Model (Type 1)

The active component and lipid are combined to form a solid solution that becomes SLN Type 1. When the cold homogenization process is used to create SLNs, a solid solution can be obtained. A lipid blend with the active ingredient is dispersed molecule-wise. This mixture is crushed in its solid stage after solidification to prevent or reduce the enlargement of active molecules in various lipid nanoparticle portions.

Drug-Enriched Shell Model (Type 2)

This model is achieved when SLNs are made using the hot technique with a low concentration of the active ingredient in the melted lipid. The lipid will precipitate first, and the concentration of active molecules in the remaining melt will steadily increase as the hot oil-in-water (o/w) nano-emulsion cools. An outer shell containing both lipid and active ingredients will solidify, resulting in burst release due to the enrichment of the particle's exterior. By adding coenzyme, the proportion of active components in the outer shell of a controlled shell model can be adjusted.

Drug-Enriched Core Model (Type 3)

Core models occur when the concentration of the active substance in the lipid melt is high and close to its saturation solubility. In most cases, the solubility of the active ingredient in the melt decreases as the heated oil droplets cools. A drug-enriched core is formed when active molecules precipitate out of solution due to exceeding saturation solubility.

Fig 5: Schematic Diagram of Drug Incorporation Model

CHARACTERIZATION OF SOLID LIPID NANOPARTICLE:

Particle Size:

Photon Correlation Spectroscopy (PCS): This method is suitable for measuring particles in the range of 3 nm to 3 μ m and is based on dynamic laser light scattering caused by Brownian motion of particles in solution or suspension. The amount of light scattering from the nanoparticles determines the hydrodynamic diameters. Since nanoparticles are often polydisperse, the population's size distribution can be gauged using the polydispersity index (P.I.). The P.I. for a polydisperse system should be less than 0.5, whereas the P.I. for a mono-disperse system is theoretically zero⁴⁶⁻⁴⁷.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM):

Determines overall form and morphology, including both particle size and distribution, using electrons transmitted through the object.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM):

Determines the general form and morphology of the specimen using electrons released from it.

Scanned Probe Microscopes:

Measures the surface of the specimen using a probe.

Polarization Intensity Differential Scattering (PIDS):

Measures particle sizes as small as 40 nm.

Field Flow Fractionation (FFF):

Separates particles based on size, using a parabolic flow profile. All eluted fractions are examined using multi-angle light scattering (MALS), which measures the particle scattering signal and computes the size-weighted radius.

X-ray Diffraction (XRD):

Helps identify polymorphic shifts and eliminates aggregates larger than 1 μ m, aiding in the identification of the compound's crystalline nature.

Freeze-Fracture Electron Microscopy:

Used to examine the solid spherical structure with no internal lamellae.

Gel Chromatography:

Separates particles based on size.

Static Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (SIMS):

Analyses the molecular composition of the surface.

Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM):

Establishes the particles' initial, unaltered shape and surface characteristics.

Surface Element Analysis:

- X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS): Used for chemical analysis.
- Amplitude-Weighted Phase Structure Determination
- Electrophoresis
- Laser Doppler Anemometry

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC):

Provides insights into the melting behaviour and crystallization of solid and lipid constituents of the particles.

- Density:
- Helium Compression Pycnometer
- Contact Angle Measurement
- Hydrophobic Interaction Chromatography

Molecular Analysis:

- Proton Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (H-NMR): Analyses molecular mobility within solid lipid nanoparticles.
- Infrared Analysis: Assesses the structural properties of lipids.

APPLICATION OF SOLID LIPID NANOPARTICLE:

Compared to liposomes, solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) are more stable and can be scaled up more easily for production. This characteristic is crucial for various targeting strategies. SLNs serve as colloidal drug delivery systems that are biodegradable and have a shelf life of at least one year. They can transport medications to actively phagocytic cells in the liver, both in vivo and in

vitro. SLNs have numerous potential uses (Mukherjee S. et al., 2009)48.

A. SLNs as Gene Vector Carriers:

SLNs can be formulated as gene vectors. In one study, SLN gene vectors were modified to include a diametric HIV-1 HAT peptide (TAT 2) to enhance gene transfer. Recent findings (Rudolph C et al., 2004)49. Have described multiple instances of SLNs containing genetic/peptide components, including DNA, plasmid DNA, and other nucleic acids. Lipid-nucleic acid nanoparticles, created by dissolving lipid and DNA separately in a liquid nano phase containing water and a water-miscible organic solvent, produced stable, uniformly sized lipid-nucleic acid nanoparticles (70–100 nm), referred to as geospheres. By incorporating a conjugated antibody-lipo polymer into the particle, it is specifically targeted.

B. SLNs for Topical Use:

Drugs like tropolide, imidazole, antifungals, anticancer agents, vitamin A, isotretinoin, ketoconazole, DNA, flurbiprofen, and glucocorticoids have all been applied topically using SLNs and nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs). Epidermal targeting is achieved as podophyllotoxin-SLN penetrates both the skin surface and the stratum corneum. Vitamin A-loaded nanoparticles can be made with glyceryl behenate. These techniques are beneficial for increasing penetration with prolonged release. Lipid nanoparticles loaded with isotretinoin were designed for topical medication delivery. Tween 80 and soy lecithin were used in the heat homogenization process. This approach enhances cumulative absorption of isotretinoin in the skin.

C. SLNs as Cosmeceuticals:

SLNs have been utilized as active carrier agents for UV blockers and sunscreens. An in vivo study demonstrated that adding 4% SLN to a regular cream increased skin moisture by 31% after 4 weeks. SLNs and NLCs are novel occlusive

topicals with regulated release. Glyceryl behenate SLNs showed improved vitamin A localization in the higher layers of skin compared to traditional formulations.

D. SLNs for Potential Agricultural Applications:

In comparison to emulsions, essential oil derived from *Artemisia arborescens* L. slowed the evaporation rate when added to SLNs. These systems have been used in agriculture as suitable vehicles for environmentally safe pesticides. The SLNs were produced with poloxamer 188 or Miranol Ultra C32 as the surfactant and Compritol 888 ATO as the lipid.

SLNs as Targeted Carriers for Anticancer Drugs:

SLNs can be used as drug carriers for the treatment of tumours. Tamoxifen, an anticancer drug, is added to SLNs to improve permeability and retention while extending the drug's release following intravenous delivery for breast cancer treatment. Drugs like methotrexate and camptothecin-loaded SLNs have been used to target tumours.

E. SLNs in Breast Cancer and Lymph Node Metastases:

Local injections of SLNs loaded with mitoxantrone were developed to reduce toxicity while enhancing medication safety and absorption. It has been observed that doxorubicin (Dox) is more effective when incorporated into SLNs. To create Dox-loaded solid lipid nanoparticles, Dox was complexed with an anionic polymer derived from soybean oil and then dispersed in water with a lipid. This technology has reduced breast cancer cells and increased efficacy.

F. Oral SLNs in Antitubercular Chemotherapy:

Antitubercular drugs, such as isoniazid, rifampicin, and SLN systems loaded with pyrazinamide, can reduce dosing frequency and

enhance patient adherence. The emulsion solvent diffusion process was used to generate these SLNs loaded with antitubercular drugs. It has also been found that nebulization of these drugs in SLNs improves their bioavailability in animals.

G. Stealth Nanoparticles:

Stealth nanoparticles offer a novel method of drug administration by evading rapid clearance by the immune system. These nanoparticles can theoretically target specific cells. Research utilizing antibody-labelled stealth lipobodies has demonstrated enhanced targeting to the intended tissue. Drugs and marker molecules have been used to evaluate stealth SLNs in animal models with success⁵⁰.

CONCLUSION:

This work concludes that persistent issues of poor drug solubility, absorption challenges, fat metabolism, and significant variability in drug plasma levels due to food effects have historically undermined the efficacy of conventional oral drug delivery systems. However, the advent of solid lipid nanoparticles (SLNs) in the past decade presents a promising new approach. SLNs offer significant improvements by enhancing the delivery of lipophilic and weakly water-soluble drugs, effectively addressing many limitations faced by traditional systems. Their ability to improve drug stability and bioavailability suggests a transformative shift in oral drug delivery, highlighting the potential for SLNs to optimize therapeutic efficacy and pave the way for future innovations in the field.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

The author declare that there is no conflict of interest in this manuscript

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The author extend their appreciation to P.S.V College of Pharmaceutical Science and Research for their invaluable infrastructure support acknowledging their crucial support.

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HOW TO CITE: Thabasoom E. , Sridevi M. , Keerthana V. , Vignesh S. , Sriramcharan Pitta , Enhanced Oral Bioavailability Through Nanoparticle- Based Solid Lipid Carrier: A Novel Approach To Drug Deliver, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 9, 1587-1602. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13863137>

